

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

THE INVESTIGATION OF MENTAL TOUGHNESS COMPONENTS OF TAEKWONDO ATHLETES OF LATVIA

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Abstract

This study was aimed to investigate mental toughness components of taekwondo athletes of Latvia. Forty taekwondo athletes (n=40, 17 – 23 years old, at least 10 years in the national and international championship) were the subjects. The athletes answered the Latvian version of the Sports Mental Toughness Questionnaire (SMTQ). All computations were performed using SPSS software version 26. The comparison of the results of the research showed there was a statistically significant difference in the confidence component of mental toughness, but control and constancy didn't change. As mental toughness plays a vital role in athletes' preparation, coaches should put mental training in their plans.

Keywords: *mental toughness, confidence, constancy, control, taekwondo*

Introduction

The theory of mental toughness highlights the importance of cognitive skills. Not only does a successful athlete need to have a high standard of physical skill needed for his sport, but the ability to cope with the pressure, the opponent, or the training can have a decisive role in his sporting career and mental health.

The first idea of mental toughness was, however, not inside sports science. The first shots fired in the cognitive revolution in America were in the mid-1950s from MIT and coincided with the advent of computers. Noam Chomsky is the most notable name associated with the beginnings of cognitive sciences. The mental movement began to take hold in America in the 1960s after Miller and Bruner founded the Harvard Center for Cognitive Studies. Cognitive science became an interdisciplinary discipline (psychology, philosophy, linguistics, anthropology, neuroscience, and computer science) (Miller, 2003). Likewise, cognitive psychology began to study intelligence, language, thinking, problem-solving, memory, attention, and perception. Cognitive theory endeavored to bridge the gap between the brain and mind (Miller, 2003).

The winner's mentality is not about winning; it is about behaving and thinking like a winner. Athletes need the mindset to excel, succeed, and be the best they can be. Winners know how to concentrate and focus, overcome obstacles, not lose sight of their goals, learn from defeats, overcome discouragement and frustration, and perform maximally. Winners know how to maintain a winning attitude even in failure. This is a positive mindset. The core mental skills utilized in the winner's mentality are goal setting, visualization, feelazation (like emotive imagery), energy management, practical thinking, and mental toughness. The winner's mentality cannot be achieved without achieving mental toughness. One could say that mental toughness as a cognitive construct is synonymous with the winner's mentality. Mental toughness is a somewhat elusive concept to define, yet it is a quality that every coach desires in their athletes, covets, and sports fans everywhere admire. Mention a sports hero or legend; a common trait will be mental toughness. Mental toughness takes on special significance because it is not maintainable without its peak performance. Mental toughness benefits include increased confidence, control of individual performance, emotion management, and emotional endurance regarding long-term goal acquisition (Reese, 1998). Achieving mental toughness is the winner's mentality.

Mental toughness is possessing the persistence and resilience of a winner (Reese, 1998) and further describing this illusory construct, including the ability to re-focus and re-concentrate. In addition, mental toughness also includes accepting responsibility and accountability for actions and their results – both successes and failures. Without mental toughness, one cannot fully achieve the winner's mentality. Every study that includes the construct of mental toughness has just as many definitions. Since the pioneering work of Loehr in the mid-1980s, the term *mental*

toughness has become synonymous with sporting greatness. Following Loehr's regular interactions with elite American athletes, he identified a highly relevant construct that has become a frequently used Layman's term for individual tolerance to stress and performance maximization. While the work of Loehr was essential for bringing the time mental toughness into modern-day parlance, the work was limited in its development of the construct, and it could be argued that the anecdotally based work generally lacked the rigors of a scientific approach. Over the next 20 years, interest in mental toughness was limited to that of sporting practitioners and journalists, and the term became increasingly mentioned on television and radio broadcasts.

From an applied perspective, whether one is dealing with coaches of professional sides or an under-10 football team, the one thing that they all want is mental toughness instilled into each of their players. Unfortunately, this 'toughening up' of players usually involves employing psychological skills training, hoping to fix this problem. However, as the concept of mental toughness remains a little 'ill-defined,' it is challenging to attempt to address the lack of it. From a theoretical perspective, the conceptual development of mental toughness will benefit from considering related constructs. Existing relevant constructs include Resilience (Dyer et al., 1996), Hardiness (Kobasa, 1979), and Physiological Toughness (Dienstbier, 1989), and most of the terms have their roots firmly in health psychology. Kobasa (1979) considers that hardiness is an essential factor in the way individuals perceive situations and how they decide to undertake an appropriate set of actions. Kobasa proposed three components of Hardiness (control, challenge, and commitment). These components are briefly summarized as follows. Power is "expressed as a tendency to feel and act as if one is influential (rather than helpful) in the face of the varied contingencies of life" (Kobasa et al., 1982). The definition of mental toughness is highly narrow and, at the same time, is open to broad interpretation by the subjects. Also, there is no way to determine the tense or honesty of the reports. Clough and his team (Clough et al., 2002) took another existing model, the 3 C's model, which was initially an existential psychological theory of hardiness (Kobasa, 1979), and by adding one more component of "confidence," Clough used it in the sports field. The final 4 C's model consisted of commitment, challenge, control, and confidence.

In taekwondo, athletes try to reach the highest level of body and mind development. In taekwondo, "a person gains self-satisfaction, peace of mind, a strong body, and becomes a master of self-defense art" (Park, 2003). Taekwondo is a martial art that allows athletes to develop traits parents desire to cultivate in their children, along with a sense of well-being within

the participant (Kim, 1985). “Central to the proposed benefits of martial arts is a belief in the ability to achieve higher levels of personal well-being through dedicated training practices” (Mainland, 2010). Taekwondo does this by combining both mental and physical activities in a constructive leisure activity. Taekwondo empowers athletes to achieve specific goals by mastering certain physical and mental actions. Taekwondo is a combat sport that has evolved in scientific and technological aspects since its inclusion as an Olympic discipline, forcing countries to seek information from the different variables involved in the sport process to achieve the best international results. Present-day taekwondo adheres to a philosophy like its ancient predecessor’s (Park et al., 2000), with psychological, physical, and spiritual aspects often incorporated into training (Lee, 2010). Practitioners are expected to display respect for themselves and others, humility, perseverance, self-control, and honesty to better ascribe to the guiding principles of martial art (Park et al., 2000). The research focusing on taekwondo’s impact on psychological health, although limited, suggests it is associated with several positive outcomes. These include increased cognitive and affective self-regulation and prosocial behavior in children (Lakes et al., 2004) and reduced aggressive behavior in youth and undergraduate populations (Harwood et al., 2017). Studies have also demonstrated improvements in mood (Yang et al., 2018) and enhanced strategies for coping with and managing stress (Petrovic, 2017) in taekwondo athletes. However, taekwondo has not yet been comprehensively examined in psychological research.

Mental toughness may be seen even more crucial in martial arts, not only if the pressure of competitions and performance is assumed, which is alike in many other sports, but more importantly, contact fighting (or even full-contact), sometimes extended life-term learning, and negative energy control during the fight when the focus is critical may be very demanding. The aspects of full contact practice, body to body, and dealing with violence and negative energy make martial arts a fruitful area for testing mental toughness and its development, as well as exploring the application and influences of cognitive skills training. Mental toughness in martial arts is a current topic of sports research. The phenomenon of mental toughness entered the research field more than 20 years ago, but we cannot say the same thing about mental toughness in Taekwondo and martial arts. Solanki and Singh (2013) about mental toughness have tested the difference between taekwondo athletes and cricket players. As the combination may seem irrelevant, the results are surprising. In this research, cricket players scored higher in handling pressure, rebound and motivation overall mental toughness. The authors suggested it may be because of the importance of the

team in a competition, whereas taekwondo athletes face the challenges alone. The team may play a crucial role in motivation and dealing with pressure. In other research, wrestling athletes took part in research regarding mental toughness and concentration. Finally, no significant correlation was found. The author, therefore claimed mental toughness and concentration did not influence each other. However, the idea of increasing mental toughness during the career was supported. International-level athletes and, therefore more advanced ones scored higher than those on a national level (Bhardwaj et al., 2014). Singh and Solanki (2015) were interested in the differences in mental toughness between judo and taekwondo athletes. In their study, 40 athletes were randomly selected (50% male and 50% female). However, no significant correlation was found between the style and the mental toughness score. This may suggest that the style of martial arts is not so important the improvement of mental toughness; nevertheless, to achieve appropriate conditions, it is necessary to choose such which is in balance within individual's opinion. Even though the authors did not find any difference, they decided to take gender into account. That is not very common in martial arts studies. On the one hand, it could provide important data and lead to future fields. But also, the area of martial arts maintains a more masculine community. Therefore, it is difficult, and in some styles/disciplines, almost impossible to reach equal representation of the genders in the research. In the research mentioned before, Bhardwaj, Singh, and Rathee (2014) studied the mental toughness of wrestlers. They found that females had a higher score in the Mental Toughness scale than males. An opposite result has been found by Azaiez et al. (2013). In the study, 12 mental skills were tested in both male and female judo, boxing, wrestling and karate athletes. No significant difference was found in the results of Ottawa the a Mental Skills Assessment Tool between the genders during both competition and training. However, this study reveals that there is a lack of management skills for fears, emotions, and stress. Applying the measurement of mental toughness on judo (Japanese martial arts,) Heiny (2012) discovered that mental toughness and self-esteem could be protective factors for aggression. A negative correlation between self-esteem and mental toughness on one side and aggression and hostility on the other side was described. In this research, males (94) and females (46) participated. The author has noticed the growing study of mental toughness and decided to apply it the martial arts, which was the main goal. The context of martial arts mental toughness is "unique", according to Heiny. This discipline requires certain body contact and is realized in an octagon ("cage"). Because of high emotional and stressful demands the authors therefore asked if there is any correlation between the mental toughness and a level of performance.

Dividing the athletes into three groups (professional, semiprofessional, and amateur) a significant difference was found between them. As expected, professionals scored higher than semi-professionals and those scored higher than amateurs. These findings suggested the athlete must develop specific mental skills during the career and must score high on them to succeed and increase the level of the competition's difficulty. The authors accordingly appeal for further research dealing with mental toughness in martial arts and inclusion mental toughness training into the workouts. This opinion is also shared by Mînjînă (2014). only 5 – 10% of athletes their training time is spent developing essential psychological skills such as mental toughness (Truelove, 2014). In the Latvian sports environment, it is often observed that in case of an unsuccessful performance, athletes, and their coaches plan to adjust their physical or technical fitness routine, perceiving the psychological aspect as less important (Astafičevs et al., 2020), also to the knowle of researchers, there wasn't any research regarding mental toughness component in Latvian taekwondo athletes, and understanding the components of mental toughness will help coaches to use mental skill training and improve their athletes mental toughness so this research planned. The aim of the research was an investigation of mental toughness component of top taekwondo athletes from Latvia and to answer this question that how mental toughness in taekwondo athletes is. Based on the above, the topic of the research “an investigation of mental toughness component of top taekwondo athletes from Latvia” was determined.

Material and methods

Participants: The study participants were 40 taekwondo athletes from 6 taekwondo clubs (female n=22, male n=18). The criteria for athletes were aged 17 to 23 years old, athletes have at least 10 years of experience in their sport, are active athletes, have succeeded in their sport and has experience in Latvian and international competitions.

Methods: The Latvian version of the Sports Mental Toughness Questionnaire (SMTQ) (Astafičevs et al., 2020) was identified and analyzed for the implementation of the task. Three parameters are analyzed through the SMTQ. First is confidence, which is characterized as a positive interpretation of threats and stress by the athlete. Second is constancy, which is an insight into how strong an athlete's commitment is to complete the set and planned tasks to the end. Third is control which shows how well or poorly an athlete can control oneself in situations where he/she begins to worry about poor performance. The answer options are ranked on a Likert scale from A to D, where A stands for „Very true” and D stands for „Not at

all.” Items 1 – 6 measure Confidence; 7 – 10 measure Constancy; 11 – 14 measure Control. Confidence scores range from 6 – 24; Constancy and Control scores range from 4 – 16; Composite scores range from 14 – 56. Items 1 – 8 are positively scored (i.e., A=4, B=3, C=2, D=1). Items 9 – 14 are negatively scored (i.e., A=1, B=2, C=3, D=4), (Sheard et al., 2009).

Procedure: The participants of the study were addressed and asked to agree to complete the sports mental toughness questionnaire survey as part of the study. After obtaining the consent of the participants, indicating that their answers are confidential and will be used only for the purpose of the study, as well as after explaining the study methodology, athletes were given a questionnaire to complete each survey statement, as well as their personal information – age, level of sport, sporting experience and achievements. In the end, the data were collected and analyzed using data analyses.

Statistical Analysis: The descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and an analysis of variance (ANOVA), Pearson correlation were conducted to determine whether there were significant differences and relationship in the components of the mental toughness of Latvian taekwondo athletes.

Results

The gender information is shown in figure 1. The range of values for each variable is shown in figure 2. The boxplot shows that for confidence, most values are between 12 and 22. For Constancy, the range of values is between 7.5 and around 16. Lastly, for Control, the range of values is between 7.5 and about 14.

Figure 1. Gender information

Figure 2. Boxplot of each SMTQ measure

The following part of the analysis is to see if there is a statistically significant difference between males and females as well as characterize each gender by its most dominant characteristic (confidence, constancy, or control).

-The hypothesis for the study is that taekwondo athletes have significant and mental solid toughness components (confidence, control, constancy). To test for significance between the groups (gender: male, female), the mean, standard deviation (Tables 1 – 3) and an analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Table 2), and Pearson correlation were conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in components of mental toughness (confidence, constancy, and control) according to sports mental toughness questionnaire by gender.

Table 1

Mean comparison of mental toughness component in gender

confidence	Male	18	15.7222	2.05242	.48376
	Female	22	17.8182	3.86235	.82346

Results show for confidence; the p-value is lower than 5%, p-value of $0.045 < 0.05$ at a 5% level of significance, which means that there is a statistically significant difference between males and females in terms of confidence. However, for constancy and control, the p-value is significantly higher than 5%, which means no difference between males and females.

Table 2

ANOVA for athletes' comparison

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
confidence	Between Groups	43.491	1	43.491	4.294	.045*
	Within Groups	384.884	38	10.129		
	Total	428.375	39			
constancy	Between Groups	.036	1	.036	.010	.922
	Within Groups	142.364	38	3.746		
	Total	142.400	39			
control	Between Groups	2.627	1	2.627	.761	.389
	Within Groups	131.273	38	3.455		
	Total	133.900	39			

(Significant*)

Also, in Table 1 and 2, confidence shows the most difference between males and females on average and the females are more confident than males.

Table 3

Overall comparison of components across gender

gender		conf	constant	ctrl
Male	Mean	15.7222	12.6667	10.1667
	N	18	18	18
	Std. Deviation	2.05242	1.97037	1.29479
Female	Mean	17.8182	12.7273	10.6818
	N	22	22	22
	Std. Deviation	3.86235	1.90693	2.21222
Total	Mean	16.8750	12.7000	10.4500
	N	40	40	40
	Std. Deviation	3.31421	1.91083	1.85293

The overall composition of components across the gender is in Table 3; The comprehensive report shows that confidence is more robust in females. The rest of the components are approximately the same in males and females; the control tool part was in the lower level.

Based on the results of toughness range, as seen in figure 3, most of the Latvian taekwondo athletes had moderate mental toughness.

Figure 3. Mental toughness range in taekwondo athletes

Lastly the relationship between the components is explored using Pearson correlation. The results are summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Correlation plot

Control and Confidence show the highest correlation of around 0.6. However, Constancy has 0.3 correlation with both Confidence and Control, which is not very significant.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate and analyze the components of the mental toughness of Latvian taekwondo athletes. The Latvian version of SMTQ (Astafičevs et al., 2020) was identified and analyzed for the implementation of the task. The descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and an analysis of variance (ANOVA), based on the results of the study, as the only component of mental toughness that is significant, is confidence and just in female taekwondo athletes. Other components (control and constancy) were not substantial, and the mental toughness range in Latvian taekwondo athletes was moderate.

Mental toughness, in scientific literature, is described as one of the most widely used but least understood terms in sports psychology. “Congenital or established psychological dominance over one’s opponent, which helps to maintain perseverance, self-confidence and act effectively in high-stress situations during the most responsible moments of competitions” (Jones et al., 2002). Taekwondo is a combat sport that has evolved in scientific and technological aspects since its inclusion as an Olympic discipline, forcing countries to seek information from the different variables involved in the sport process to achieve the best international results. The most significant performance gains come from prescribing an optimal amount of physical training with appropriate psychological skills to allow for the best adaptation before competition. Mental toughness and its components are important in martial arts and, taekwondo, Gucciardi (2011) stated there is a positive relation between time (years of training, hours of

exercise per week) to the desire to achieve, attentional control and global mental toughness attribute, the idea of increasing mental toughness during the career was supported. International-level athletes and, therefore more advanced ones scored higher than those on a national level (Bhardwaj et al., 2014).

Conclusion

The obtained data from the research concluded that based on the results of the study as the only component of mental toughness that is significant is confidence, and just in female taekwondo athlete. The components of control and constancy were not important. Other researchers should try to find out ways to increase the mental toughness of taekwondo athletes and other sports. The SMTQ is a useful tool for testing mental toughness, emphasizing that participants come from an extensive variety of sports and compete on different levels, from regional to international.

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